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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL ONCOPATHOLOGY OF THE POPULATION OF GRODNO, BREST AND GOMEL REGIONS IN THE POST-CHERNOBYL PERIOD

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Annotation: The features of oncological morbidity were studied and a comparative analysis was carried out in the areas of the population of the Gomel region, the most affected by radiation in the post-Chernobyl period, the Brest and Grodno regions, which have average indicators of radiation pollution in the republic. As a result of the conducted research, the tendency of the increase in the incidence of malignant diseases in the population of the Republic of Belarus over the past 20 years has been established. The predominant growth of oncological pathology is observed among urban residents rather than rural ones.

Keywords: cancer incidence, post-Chernobyl period

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РЕГИОНАЛЬНОЙ ОНКОПАТОЛОГИИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ГРОДНЕНСКОЙ, БРЕСТСКОЙ И ГОМЕЛЬСКОЙ ОБЛАСТЕЙ В ПОСТЧЕРНОБЫЛЬСКИЙ ПЕРИОД

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Аннотация: Изучены особенности онкологической заболеваемости и проведен сравнительный анализ в районах проживания населения Гомельской области, наиболее пострадавших от радиации в постчернобыльский период, Брестской и Гродненской областей, которые имеют средние показатели радиационного загрязнения по республике. В результате проведенного исследования установлена тенденция увеличения заболеваемости злокачественными заболеваниями среди населения Республики Беларусь за последние 20 лет. Преимущественный рост онкологической патологии наблюдается среди городских жителей, а не сельских.

Ключевые слова: онкологическая заболеваемость, постчернобыльский период

Relevance. Currently, there is an increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms all over the world. Over the past 10 years in the Republic of Belarus, the annual increase in malignant neoplasms has amounted to 1115 cases per 100 thousand population. In 2019, 52,987 new cases of malignant neoplasms were registered in the Republic of Belarus. Reducing the morbidity and mortality of the population from malignant neoplasms is one of the most important problems facing medical science and healthcare at the present time [1, 2].

Radiation can cause various stochastic effects, which can lead to changes in the cellular genome and be the cause of cancer pathology. As a

result of the explosion at the fourth unit of the Chernobyl nuclear power plant on April 26, 1986, the territory of Belarus was intensely contaminated with radioactive isotopes released into the atmosphere.

Radioactive contamination of the territory of the Republic of Belarus affected the entire territory to varying degrees, the Gomel, Mogilev and Brest regions were the most affected. There were 3,678 settlements in the pollution zone, in which 2.2 million people lived. 479 settlements have ceased to exist. The area of the exclusion zone (evacuation) is 1.7 thousand square kilometers.

Today, 21 districts are among the most affected. Almost 1104 thousand people live in settlements located in zones of radioactive contamination, 91.5 % of them live in a zone of residence with periodic radiation monitoring (1-5 Ku / sq. km).

The negative impact on all spheres of life continues, and it is impossible to be sure that the most negative consequences for human health are already behind. Even now, in some areas that have been contaminated, there are extremely high concentrations of radioactive isotopes in soil and plants.

The problem of radiation negative effects on the human body has been and remains the most urgent and is in the focus of Public Health and medical science [6].

Goal. The purpose of this study was to study the characteristics and comparative analysis of cancer incidence in the areas of the population of the Gomel region, the most affected by radiation in the post-Chernobyl period, the Brest and Grodno regions, which have average indicators of radiation pollution in the republic.

Materials and methods of research. The territorial features of the spread of cancer in the Gomel, Brest, Grodno regions and their dynamics have been studied.

For the analysis of the three-time interval: 2000, 2009 and 2019.

The rates of spread of the incidence of malignant neoplasms in the population of the Brest, Gomel and Grodno regions were studied. Analytical, epidemiological and comparative evaluation methods were used to study official statistical data on the incidence of malignant neoplasms in the population of the Republic of Belarus, as well as literature data on the incidence of malignant neoplasms in our country [3-7].

Results and their discussion. The incidence of oncological diseases among the population throughout the republic has been growing markedly since 2000. In 2000, 310.1 cases of malignant neoplasms per 100 thousand population were detected among urban residents and 372.0 – among rural residents. In 2009, the incidence among urban residents amounted to 406,1 people per 100 thousand people, among the rural population – 459,3. In 2019, the incidence per 100 thousand population was 563.8 among urban residents and 604,8 among rural residents. The increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms over 19 years is 81 % among urban residents, while among the rural population – 62 %.

In 2009, the incidence rates of oncological diseases in the regions of the Republic of Belarus were: in the Grodno region – 401.0; in the Brest region – 358.2; in the Gomel region – 447.6 people per 100 thousand population.

In 2019, in the Grodno region, the incidence per 100 thousand population was 526.0 among urban residents and 661.8 among the rural population. In the Brest region, 529.2 cases of malignant neoplasms among urban residents and 559.0 among rural residents were detected per 100 thousand population. In the Gomel region, 608.6 cases per 100 thousand population were registered among urban residents, 666.5 – among rural residents.

Analyzing the patterns of spatial and temporal spread of cancer in the republic, we note that the highest incidence rates in 2019 were registered in Gomel (621.4 – per 100 thousand population). A lower incidence rate was detected in the Brest (537.8) and Grodno (558.1) regions.

The growth rate of cancer incidence reflects the influence of epidemiological risk factors both in cities and in rural areas. There is an increase in cancer incidence among urban residents, significantly exceeding that among rural residents. This pattern has persisted for many years.

The increase of cancer incidence in the 10 years from 2009 to 2019 were: Grodno oblast – 39,2 %; Brest region – 50,1 %; Gomel region – 38,8 %.

Based on the data obtained, we can conclude about the rapid growth in the number of people with cancer in different parts of our country. A predominant increase in cancer incidence among residents of

the Brest region has been established in comparison with other regions of the republic.

The incidence rates among women and men are somewhat different. Thus, in the Brest region, as of 2019, 556.5 cases of the disease were detected per 100 thousand of the population among men and 492.8 cases per 100 thousand of the population among women. In the Gomel and Grodno regions, trends persist. In the Grodno region: men – 597.3 cases of malignant neoplasms per 100 thousand population; women – 533.6. In the Gomel region: men – 666.4 cases of malignant neoplasms per 100 thousand population; women – 582.2 [4-7].

Among nosological oncological diseases in 2019 in the Republic of Belarus, the first in terms of localization frequency are: in men, prostate cancer takes 1st place (20.7 %), lung cancer takes 2nd place (15.9 %), colorectal cancer takes 3rd place (11.9 %); in women, breast cancer takes 1st place (22.8 %), 2nd place – colorectal cancer (12.5 %), 3rd place – uterine body cancer (10.8 %) and somewhat less often ovarian cancer (4.6 %) and cervical cancer (4.1 %).

Conclusions. As a result of the conducted studies, the tendency of the increase in the incidence of malignant neoplasms in the population of the Republic of Belarus over the past 20 years has been established. The predominant growth of oncopathologies is observed among urban residents rather than rural ones.

The Gomel Region, the most affected by radionuclide contamination, remains the leader among the regions of the Republic of Belarus in terms of the incidence of malignant neoplasms in the post-Chernobyl period. We have identified a significant increase in the incidence among the residents of the Brest region in the period from 2009 to 2019, exceeding the growth in other regions of the country. In the Grodno region, there is also a tendency to increase the incidence of malignant neoplasms.

The results of the study suggest a significant rate of increase in the incidence of lung cancer, breast cancer, colorectal cancer in the analyzed areas. Comparing the incidence of oncopathologies among the male and female populations, we found a pattern according to which malignant neoplasms are detected much more often in men than in women.

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